

Transport and competitive sorption-desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in diverse agricultural soils under high flow rates and various concentration ratios

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ABSTRACT

An inverse model based on the maximum likelihood method, incorporating various sorption–desorption isotherms, was applied to column experiments to capture the single and competitive sorption–desorption and leaching of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in agricultural soils with varying organic–inorganic content. The study simulates high irrigation or heavy rainfall to evaluate chemical behaviour under intense leaching, accounting for compound interactions, concentration ratios, and flow rates within equilibrium and kinetic frameworks. Results show Triton X-100's transport is largely unaffected by glyphosate, whereas its presence significantly reduces glyphosate's sorption and retardation, slightly decreasing overall soil sorption capacity (soil A 7%, B 5%, C 10%, D 6%). Kinetic Langmuir models capture time-dependent sorption–desorption dynamics most accurately ($R^2 > 0.85$). Soil mineralogy (Albite, Illite, Kaolinite) and metal content (Al, K, Fe) enhance glyphosate sorption, retardation, and tailing, but have minimal effect on Triton X-100. Doubling the concentration ratio reduced glyphosate's kinetic sorption coefficient by up to 10% and overall sorption capacity by 16%, while increasing flow rate from 2 to 3 mL/min decreased the sorption coefficient by 20%, slightly increased desorption, and reduced sorption capacity from ~36% to 16%. Results ultimately show sorption–desorption behaviour under high-flow competitive conditions depends strongly on environmental factors and cannot be generalized across scenarios.

1. Introduction

Pesticides and surfactants are classified as micropollutants due to their low concentrations in the environment (Wilms et al., 2023). Despite these low concentrations, their chemical properties and potential leaching in subsurface environments pose significant contamination risks for soil and groundwater resources (Åkesson et al., 2013; Chaudhary et al., 2024). During conditions of heavy rainfall or high irrigation, these compounds are particularly prone to high leaching, which increases the likelihood of groundwater contamination (Moghimi et al., 2025c, 2024; Schaefer et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021). The transport and ultimate fate of these compounds in soil and consequently in groundwater are influenced primarily by mechanisms such as dispersion and sorption impacted by soil organic–inorganic content (De Gerónimo and Aparicio, 2022), concentration levels, and the rainfall of

irrigation rates (Yuan et al., 2023).

The simultaneous application of pesticides and surfactants is a common agricultural practice; however, their leaching and reactive transport cannot be generalized due to differences in their chemical structures and sorption–desorption behaviours (Ponnuchamy et al., 2021). Glyphosate and Triton X-100, commonly used as a pesticide and surfactant respectively (Costa et al., 2023), are often applied together to enhance pesticide effectiveness (Li et al., 2023). Understanding their competitive sorption–desorption behaviour is therefore essential for evaluating their transport dynamics and potential leaching risks to groundwater (Castro et al., 2013). The interactions of these compounds with soil are affected by factors such as soil composition (Rana et al., 2023), concentration ratios (Checa-Fernández et al., 2023), and flow rates (Sainz et al., n.d.). Standard laboratory-scale column experiments (Kumar et al., 2023; Refaey et al., 2017), provide insights into transport

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and sorption–desorption mechanisms under dynamic conditions (Schmidová et al., 2020). To accurately quantify single and competitive sorption–desorption, experimental data must be analysed using suitable competitive isotherms within equilibrium-kinetic frameworks (Moghimi et al., 2025a). This approach enables estimation of sorption–desorption coefficients and characterizing their behaviours and generating reliable parameters for large-scale models (Dhuldhaj et al., 2022).

Previous studies have investigated the sorption and transport of glyphosate (Besghaier et al., 2021; Gairhe et al., 2021) and Triton X-100 (Wiśniewska et al., 2021) in soil and groundwater. Despite glyphosate's strong affinity for soils, recent research shows it can still leach into groundwater (Gairhe et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2024). Its sorption and mobility are influenced by soil mineral composition (Dotor-Robayo et al., 2022), depth-dependent concentration variations (Fenn et al., 2023), and the presence of coexisting compounds (Ghavamifar et al., 2023). Triton X-100 has been widely studied for its role in enhancing contaminant transport (Jiménez-González et al., 2019) by altering solute mobility (Knoche and Bukovac, 2004) and sorption behaviour (Lu et al., 2018). The impact of Triton X-100 on contaminant desorption and mobility depends strongly on soil properties and its concentration (Ramírez-Arias et al., 2019). Some studies have investigated glyphosate's sorption in the presence of other compounds. Dotor Robayo et al. (2024) examined the effects of phosphate, used as a fertilizer, on glyphosate displacement using single sorption models. They found that adding phosphate reduced glyphosate's retention time and increased its leaching in soil. Similarly, Munira et al. (2018) studied glyphosate's binary sorption, showing that the presence of additional compounds could lower glyphosate's sorption coefficient, with variations depending on soil properties. In earlier research, Munira et al. (2016) explored cadmium's competitive effects on glyphosate sorption, observing minimal impact. While these studies assessed competition between compounds, none developed a competitive model to quantify these effects. Gimsing et al., (2004) studied competitive sorption of glyphosate and inorganic phosphate in soils and oxides, influencing their transport and potential groundwater contamination using kinetic modelling. They proposed sorption in soils involves both competitive and additive interactions, while sorption on oxides is primarily competitive. In this context, studies on leaching and sorption of various compounds often simulate agricultural field conditions under low flow rates (Huang et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2024). Although, competitive sorption–desorption of a pesticide and surfactant under high flow rates is not investigated and many studies use single models for multicomponent systems (Kiecak et al., 2020), but various equilibrium and kinetic models have been developed to examine how compounds affect each other's sorption–desorption rates in multicomponent systems (Lima et al., 2023; Padilla et al., 2023) regarding the competitive scenarios in equilibrium and kinetic conditions (Orucoglu et al., 2022; Rajabi et al., 2021). Phanikumar et al. (2022) introduced two- and three-site models for characterizing contaminant interactions in both aqueous and solid phases, while Chen et al. (2022) applied a dual-porosity model to analyse mobile and immobile phase interactions, as well as contaminant retardation. Additionally, Georgii (2021) used a multi-compound sorption model based on Langmuir isotherms to describe sorption in mixed-component conditions. Other studies have explored the transport and sorption of emerging contaminants, such as PFAS (Am et al., 2024) and surfactants with complex chemical structures (Buhani et al., 2023), using kinetic models. Several studies have also examined the effects of key factors such as temperature (Elwakeel and Yousif, 2010), initial solution pH, concentration (Moghimi et al., 2025b), and contact time (Khan et al., 2024) on the kinetic sorption behaviour, along with the application of different sorption isotherm models.

Although surfactant-facilitated transport in soil has been extensively studied (Bolan et al., 2023), and the sorption of pesticides like glyphosate is well-documented (Meftaul et al., 2021; Ogunbiyi et al., 2023), the competitive sorption–desorption of pesticides in the presence of surfactants, a common agricultural practice, remains underexplored.

Specifically, the effects of such competitive interactions on leaching, transport, and sorption–desorption under high irrigation or heavy rainfall, demonstrating intense leaching and transport are not adequately addressed (Kang et al., 2024). Additionally, the impact of pesticide/surfactant concentration ratios on sorption–desorption dynamics is not fully understood (Fenn et al., 2023). There is also a gap in comparing equilibrium and kinetic models to identify the most accurate approach for determining single and competitive sorption–desorption parameters, especially under conditions where equilibrium models may fail to capture fast-flow scenarios (Lin et al., 2016). This study combines laboratory column experiments with an inverse model based on the maximum likelihood algorithm to examine leaching and single-competitive sorption–desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100. Experiments simulate high-flow conditions, such as heavy rainfall or intense irrigation, to assess leaching potential. The effects of soil composition, concentration ratios, and flow rates on competitive sorption–desorption are quantified to evaluate generalizability. Performance of kinetic and equilibrium models is compared, highlighting the importance of kinetic models under high-flow conditions. The results provide insights for improving pesticide and surfactant management and mitigating soil and groundwater contamination under intense environmental conditions.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Agricultural soils characteristics

Four European agricultural soils with sandy texture (particle diameters 0.05–2 mm) based on their distinct characteristics including organic–inorganic composition were collected from different agricultural fields in Germany to be used in this study. Soil particle density, measured using the GAS JAR approach (Smith, 2021), and the soil pH (HI 991001N, Hanna Instruments) are presented in Table 1. Soil organic and inorganic components are measured to evaluate the factors influencing the competitive sorption of pesticide and surfactant in agricultural soils. The organic content of agricultural soils is assessed through the Loss on Ignition (LOI) method (Satoh et al., 2023). Results from the LOI method reveal that the organic matter content in soils have similar amount of the overall soil composition.

Soil mineralogy and chemical compositions are captured using complementary analytical techniques X-ray diffraction (XRD) and X-ray fluorescence (XRF), respectively. Table 2 provides a detailed overview of the minerals present in each soil type, along with their corresponding chemical formulas. It should be noted that in soils characterized with lower pH, the presence of CaCO₃ despite its typical solubility under such conditions can be attributed to prior liming practices, incomplete dissolution combined with spatial heterogeneity in soil pH, or the precipitation of CaCO₃ through reactions involving calcium ions. Also, Table 3 presents a comprehensive breakdown of the chemical compositions of our agricultural soils, highlighting the soils respective fractions.

2.2. Chemicals characteristics

Glyphosate (Merck, 1071-83-6), also known as N-(Phosphonomethyl) glycine (C₃H₈NO₅P), is an extensively utilized non-selective, systemic, and post-emergent pesticide in agriculture (Pereira et al., 2019). Triton X-100 (Merck, 9036-19-5), a versatile non-ionic surfactant

Table 1
Physio-chemical properties of four agricultural soils investigated in this study.

Parameter	Soil A	Soil B	Soil C	Soil D
Particle density (g/cm ³)	2.542	2.483	2.576	2.491
pH	6.52	6.64	7.18	6.56
Organic content (%)	3.234	3.456	3.341	3.286

Table 2

XRD results for the mineralogy of the agricultural soils. The diamond figure (◆) shows the presence of the mineral in agricultural soils.

Mineral	Chemical formulation	Soil	Soil	Soil	Soil
		A	B	C	D
Quartz	SiO ₂	◆	◆	◆	◆
Albite	Na Al Si ₃ O ₈	◆	–	◆	–
Microcline	K Al Si ₃ O ₈	◆	–	◆	–
Muscovite	K Al ₂ (Al Si ₃ O ₁₀) (F, OH) ₂	◆	◆	◆	◆
Illite	(K, H ₃ O) (Al Mg Fe) ₂ (Si Al) ₄ O ₁₀ [(OH) ₂ (H ₂ O)]	◆	◆	◆	◆
Gibbsite	Al (OH) ₃	◆	–	–	–
Kaolinite	Al ₂ Si ₂ O ₅ (OH) ₄	◆	–	◆	–
Orthoclase	K Al Si ₃ O ₈	◆	◆	–	◆
Caldecayhidrite	Ca Al ₂ O ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₀	◆	–	–	–
Koninckite	(Fe, Al) PO ₄ (H ₂ O) ₃	◆	–	◆	–
Birnessite	K _{0.5} Mn ₂ O ₄ (H ₂ O) _{1.5}	◆	–	◆	◆
Calcite	Ca CO ₃	◆	◆	◆	◆

Table 3

XRF results for the chemical composition of the agricultural soils.

Component	Chemical formulation	Fraction (%)			
		Soil A	Soil B	Soil C	Soil D
Sodium	Na	0.262	0.203	0.173	0.142
Magnesium	Mg	0.422	0.697	0.585	0.645
Aluminium	Al	6.429	6.857	6.440	6.1278
Silicon	Si	45.843	41.122	34.498	41.753
Phosphorous	P	0.304	0.435	0.161	0.326
Sulfur	S	0.137	0.314	0.149	0.192
Potassium	K	8.384	6.849	8.037	6.464
Calcium	Ca	1.879	6.350	23.547	6.138
Titanium	Ti	3.359	4.459	2.607	4.735
Manganese	Mn	0.637	0.986	0.778	3.169
Iron	Fe	29.744	25.706	28.801	24.015
Zink	Zn	0.165	0.208	0.148	0.250

(C₁₄H₂₂O (C₂H₄O)_n), is employed to evaluate the performance of glyphosate under competitive conditions. This compound is a widely used surfactant for solute transport studies in laboratory experiments (Purkait et al., 2005). Potassium bromide (Merck, 10031–22-8), an inorganic chemical is employed as a tracer for dispersion and mass conservation analysis as bromide (anions) neither sorb to nor react with soil particles. Double Deionized water (DDW) (Alto Type I Polisher, Triple Red, 18.2 M) is used for water flow and preparing stock solutions. Detections and concentration measurements of potassium bromide, glyphosate, and Triton X-100 are performed using the Ion chromatography-mass spectrometry (IC-MS) system (Valle et al., 2019). The ICMS is using Thermoscientific IC-MS instrument, which was equipped with IonPack 4 μm Infinity Lab Poroshell 120 EC-C18 (4.6 × 150 mm, AGILENT TECHNOLOGIES) column with a basic solvent of potassium hydroxide. More detailed information about the developed approach using the ICMS is provided in Appendix A.

For sorption experiments, a concentration of 100 (mg/L) for bromide and glyphosate is used in single and competitive scenarios (Rissouli et al., 2017). Also, Triton X-100 is utilized in different concentrations of 1% and 2% (surfactant weight (g)/solution volume (L)) in competitive experiments (Lin et al., 2016). These concentrations were selected based on several factors, including environmental relevance and optimization objectives. The concentration of 100 mg/L for glyphosate falls within the range of glyphosate levels reported in agricultural runoff and soil leachates, particularly in areas with intensive glyphosate usage (Brovini et al., 2021; Lajmanovich et al., 2022). Using a fixed concentration for glyphosate allows for consistent comparison across different experimental setups and ensures that observed variations in sorption and transport are due to the presence of Triton X-100 rather than fluctuations in Glyphosate concentration. This approach ensures a clear understanding of how the surfactant concentrations influence glyphosate

behaviour. The chosen concentrations for Triton X-100 are based on usage in agriculture and sufficient to modify the surface tension and enhance the wettability of soil particles, thereby change glyphosate sorption (Lin et al., 2016).

2.3. Column experiment methodology

Column test experiments closely adhere to the established Up-flow percolation test approach SIS-ISO/TS 21268-3:2019 for capturing leaching procedures in agricultural soils. These tests aim to analyse dispersive transport and competitive sorption phenomena in subsequent chemical testing. Fig. 1 illustrates the schematic diagram of the column experiment setup for studying the reactive transport of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in agricultural soils. To prepare the soil samples, they were air-dried and sieved to use particles smaller than 2 mm. These soil particles were then packed into acrylic plastic columns measuring 25 mm in inner diameter and 75 mm in length (length to diameter ratio of 3) with the mean bulk density of 1.57 (g/cm³). The soil columns were assembled in multiple layers with consistent depth, and the top and bottom of the soil were packed with Carboxite porous stones and glass fibre filters. The experiment involved passing DDW and chemical feeds through silicon tubes to inject them into the soil column. For each experiment, the soil column contents were slowly flooded with DDW from below and allowed to swell and equilibrate for 24 h at a flow rate of 1 ml/min, fully immersed in water. To achieve different flow rates for various column tests, a peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow 505i) was calibrated to provide flow rates of 1–3 ml/min. The outlet chemicals were sampled using a fraction collector (Foxy) to precisely collect samples according to the time intervals of 0.25 h and sampling volume of 2 ml. The experiment duration for both single and competitive cases was 12 h, comprising a 1-hour pre-equilibrium phase of injecting DDW, followed by a 4-hour injection of the chemical solution feed and a subsequent 7-hour injection of DDW. The final samples were subjected to IC-MS analysis to measure the concentration of chemicals after the reactions with soil components. Experiments are repeated to ensure generated data validity (Appendix B), and mass balance verification is accomplished for all of column experiments by checking the mass recovery of all three compounds. After each experiment, the effluent was collected, and the compounds concentration was measured and compared with the injection values.

The flow rates of 1, 2, and 3 ml/min (Mohammadnejad et al., 2020; Rubin et al., 2012), and even up to 6 ml/min (Kang et al., 2024; Raveh-Rubin et al., 2015), are extensively used in the literature for transport studies. The elevated flow rates simulate extreme conditions, providing insights into the behaviour of glyphosate and Triton X-100 under stress scenarios. This approach helps to understand the soil's sorption capacity and the potential risks of chemical leaching during heavy rainfall or irrigation events. Three independent column experiments were conducted to investigate the impacts of column size on the transport of bromide as a tracer in sandy soil and find a representative volume for the sorption experiments. The objective was to comprehend the effects of the column size and boundary conditions on dispersive solute transport and determine the optimal size for capturing the transport and sorption of glyphosate in agricultural soils. Based on these experiments, a column with dimensions of 75 mm in length and 25 mm in inner diameter was selected. Detailed information about the experiments, including the methodology and results, can be found in Appendix C.

2.4. Governing equations

The reactive transport of a solute in a porous domain is described by the one-dimensional Advection-Dispersion equation (ADE) that incorporates transport mechanisms including advection, dispersion, and sorption (Moghimi et al., 2022; Poureslami et al., 2021).

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of column experiment setup. 1) DDW, 2) Chemicals, 3) Silicon Tube, 4) Solenoid Valve, 5) Peristaltic Pump, 6) Valve, 7) Column, 8) Porous stone, 9) Fibre-Glass filter, 10) Fraction Collector, 11) Waste.

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -v \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + D_L \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

Here, t represents time (h), S is the amount of the chemical component retained by the soil ($\text{mg}/\text{g}_{\text{soil}}$), C is the concentration (mg/L), D_L is the longitudinal dispersion coefficient (cm^2/h), and v is the pore velocity (cm/h) which is calculated by using equation $v = Q/(A \cdot \epsilon)$ using volumetric flow rate Q (cm^3/h), the cross-sectional area perpendicular to the flow A (cm^2), and volumetric water content ϵ . Also, ρ is soil density ($\text{g}_{\text{soil}}/\text{cm}^3$) and S is the total concentration of solute sorbed by one gram of soil ($\text{mg}/\text{g}_{\text{soil}}$).

For sorption analysis, both equilibrium and kinetic approaches can be applied to incorporate sorption–desorption mechanism into the ADE. The equilibrium approach assumes local equilibrium conditions at each point within the soil column, while the kinetic approach accounts for temporal variations in sorption, offering a more detailed analysis. In this study, both kinetic and equilibrium methods are employed, and their accuracy and performance are quantified. First method is utilizing the local equilibrium approach, where the sorption–desorption of solute on the sorbent surface could be generalised as a function of concentration through the reformulation of the ADE equation.

$$R \frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -v \frac{\partial C}{\partial x} + D_L \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (2)$$

$$R = 1 + \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \frac{\partial S}{\partial C} \quad (3)$$

where R (-) is retardation factor that quantifies the extent to which a solute's movement is slowed down or retarded due to interactions and attachment with the soil particles. For single sorption, three standard isotherms, namely linear (Urano et al., 1984), Langmuir (Matthijs and De Henau, 1985), and Freundlich (Abe et al., 1985) isotherms, are employed.

$$\text{Linear } S = K_d \times CR = 1 + \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} K_d \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Freundlich } S = K_F \times C^m R = 1 + \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} m K_F C^{m-1} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Langmuir } S = \frac{S_{\max} K_L C}{1 + K_L C} R = 1 + \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \frac{S_{\max} K_L}{(1 + K_L C)^2} \quad (6)$$

In sorption isotherms K_d ($\text{L}/\text{g}_{\text{soil}}$), K_F ($\text{L}^m/\text{mg}^{1-m} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{soil}}$), and K_L (L/mg) are sorption parameters for the Linear, Freundlich, and Langmuir models, respectively. In the Freundlich model, m is a dimensionless exponent representing the non-linearity of the sorption mechanism. In the Langmuir model, S_{\max} ($\text{mg}/\text{g}_{\text{soil}}$) represents the maximum sorption capacity of soil. In the kinetic framework, the ADE equation incorporates the sorption variation term which means considering two equations according to the experimental time and numerical steps used.

For the single sorption, in addition to the ADE (equation (1)), the following kinetic models are used for sorption analysis (Padilla and Selim, 2021).

$$\text{Kinetic Linear } \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k_{\text{sor},d} C - k_{\text{des},d} S \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Kinetic Freundlich } \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k_{\text{sor},F} C^m - k_{\text{des},F} S \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Kinetic Langmuir } \frac{\partial S}{\partial t} = k_{\text{sor},L} C(S_{\max} - S) - k_{\text{des},L} S \quad (9)$$

In the kinetic linear model, which describes a linear pattern between sorption–desorption and concentration, the parameters $k_{\text{sor},d}$ ($\text{L}/\text{g}_{\text{soil}} \cdot \text{h}$) and $k_{\text{des},d}$ ($1/\text{h}$) are sorption and desorption constants, respectively. Freundlich model considers a nonlinear behaviour using nonlinearity term m and sorption–desorption constants $k_{\text{sor},F}$ ($\text{L}^m \cdot \text{mg}^{1-m}/\text{h} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{soil}}$) and $k_{\text{des},F}$ ($1/\text{h}$). Langmuir model considers the maximum sorption capacity of the soil S_{\max} ($\text{mg}/\text{g}_{\text{soil}}$) to describe the sorption behaviour with sorption–desorption constants $k_{\text{sor},L}$ ($\text{L}/\text{mg} \cdot \text{h}$) and $k_{\text{des},L}$ ($1/\text{h}$) (El-Korashy et al., 2016). For competitive system, the extended Langmuir model for equilibrium approach (Janetti et al., 2012) and kinetic Langmuir competitive model (Zhao et al., 2024) for kinetic approach are utilized within the multicomponent ADE accounting their interactive behaviour. These models extended were selected due to their ability to effectively represent both equilibrium and kinetic competition between solutes with distinct chemical characteristics (e.g., ionic and non-ionic compounds). These models provide a suitable balance between physical realism and computational efficiency, making them well-suited for implementation within the inverse modelling framework used in this study. Moreover, Langmuir-based formulations offer robust predictive performance for describing the competitive sorption–desorption of organic pollutants and surfactants in agricultural soils. Investigating the ability of alternative models to describe the sorption and desorption processes of the selected compounds will be the focus of future work. In competitive models, the equations for glyphosate and Triton X-100 are solved simultaneously, considering the concentration of the other compound to reflect their mutual influence on each other's sorption–desorption behaviour.

$$\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} = -v \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial x} + D_L \frac{\partial^2 C_i}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{\partial S_i}{\partial C_i} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial C_j} \frac{\partial C_j}{\partial t} \right) \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial C_j}{\partial t} = -v \frac{\partial C_j}{\partial x} + D_L \frac{\partial^2 C_j}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \left(\frac{\partial S_j}{\partial C_j} \frac{\partial C_j}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial S_j}{\partial C_i} \frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} \right)$$

The extended Langmuir model, which describes equilibrium competitive sorption among multiple solutes, is formulated as follows:

$$\text{Extended Langmuir } S_i = \frac{S_{\max} K_{L,i} C_i}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^N K_{L,j} C_j} \quad (11)$$

$$S_j = \frac{S_{\max} K_{L,j} C_j}{1 + \sum_{j=1}^N K_{L,j} C_j}$$

Therefore, to incorporate the interaction between compounds within the coupled transport-reaction equations, the sorption variation over time for each compound can be replaced by the concentration variations, which is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{\partial S_i}{\partial t} = \left(\left(\frac{\partial C_i}{\partial t} \right) \times \left(\frac{S_{\max} K_{L,i} (1 + K_{L,j} C_j)}{(1 + \sum_{j=1}^N K_{L,j} C_j)^2} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial C_j}{\partial t} \right) \times \left(\frac{S_{\max} K_{L,i} K_{L,j} C_i}{(1 + \sum_{j=1}^N K_{L,j} C_j)^2} \right) \right) \quad (12)$$

For the kinetic competitive Langmuir model, two time-dependent equations are solved simultaneously to describe the adsorption and desorption processes of the competing solutes, as follows:

$$\text{Kinetic Langmuir } \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial t} = k_{\text{sor},i} S_{\max} C_i \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^N S_j / S_{\max} \right)^{\epsilon_i} - k_{\text{des},i} S_i$$

$$\frac{\partial S_j}{\partial t} = k_{\text{sor},j} S_{\max} C_j \left(1 - \sum_{j=1}^N S_i / S_{\max} \right)^{\epsilon_j} - k_{\text{des},j} S_j \quad (13)$$

In Extended Langmuir model $K_{L,i \text{ and } j}$ (L/mg) are competitive sorption parameters for pesticide and surfactant and S_{\max} (mg/g_{soil}) represents the maximum sorption capacity of soil in the binary system. In kinetic

model $K_{\text{sor}, \text{des}, i, j}$ present the kinetic sorption (L/mg-h) and desorption (1/h) parameters and ϵ_i (-) represents the kinetic parameters (Sin et al., 2018). The extended Langmuir model is based on the assumptions that the sorbent surface contains homogeneous monolayer active sites. These assumptions enable the extension of the single-solute Langmuir equation to multicomponent systems by considering the competitive occupation of the same sorption sites by different solutes. The kinetic competitive Langmuir model assumes that sorption and desorption rate changes over time and that competition between solutes arises from the simultaneous occupation of shared sorption sites. This dynamic approach allows modelling of time-dependent behaviour under non-equilibrium conditions while accounting for competitive effects between coexisting compounds.

2.5. Maximum likelihood model

To estimate dispersion and single-competitive sorption-desorption parameters for glyphosate and Triton X-100 in agricultural soils, an inverse model utilizing a maximum likelihood algorithm was developed on the MATLAB platform. The developed maximum likelihood model (MLM) integrates an optimization algorithm with a finite difference model (FDM), enabling the simulation of multi-component transport and sorption-desorption processes within a one-dimensional framework. This model utilizes experimental data to estimate parameters, providing a robust method for determining transport and sorption-desorption dynamics based on experimental data. Fig. 2 provides an overview of the developed MLM performance, estimating the optimal transport and sorption-desorption parameters.

To model the competitive transport and sorption-desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100, the developed MLM numerically solves a

Fig. 2. Overview of the developed maximum likelihood algorithm for estimating transport and equilibrium-kinetic single-competitive sorption parameters.

coupled system of partial differential equations (PDEs) describing solute advection, dispersion, and nonlinear sorption–desorption based on the single and competitive sorption–desorption isotherm within equilibrium and kinetic frameworks. The PDEs for different sorption–desorption models are solved simultaneously for compounds using a finite difference method (FDM). For single-component systems, the FDM employs the Forward Time Central Space (FTCS) discretization scheme, while for competitive systems, the coupled PDEs are solved across the spatial domain using an implicit time integration approach in MATLAB. The mutual influence of each compound on the other's sorption behaviour was incorporated through sorption derivatives, which were embedded into a mass matrix formulation to ensure accurate coupling and stability. In parallel, the maximum likelihood algorithm relies on an optimization toolbox that leverages the “fmincon” solver in MATLAB. The inverse method feeds the experimental concentration data to the FDM solver to simulate the chemical transport and sorption–desorption according to the applied initial and boundary conditions (Moghimi et al., 2023a, 2023b). The accuracy of the developed ADE solver is validated by comparing its forward solution with results obtained from references which compared the results of analytical solution with numerical approach (Mojtabi and Deville, 2015) as detailed in Appendix D. Moreover inverse model performance for each case is analysed using evaluation indicators including the determination coefficient R^2 (–) and root mean square error RMSE (mg/L, %) (Sun et al., 2022). The developed MLM provides a robust and reliable framework for parameter estimation under both equilibrium and kinetic conditions. Although the method involves slightly higher computational time, the overall cost remains modest due to its improved accuracy and reduced need for repeated experiments, enabling calibration of the numerical models.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Single sorption

Analysis starts with the dynamics of leaching and sorption–desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100 under single-component conditions. Subsequently, this knowledge serves as the foundation for extending our investigation to competitive sorption–desorption scenarios. Detailed characteristics of each soil column used in the dynamic experiments are summarized in Table 4. Despite diverse particle

Table 4
Soil columns characteristics for independent single sorption experiments.

Parameter	Column A	Column B	Column C	Column D
<i>Glyphosate experiments</i>				
Soil Mass (g)	50.723	50.585	50.364	50.535
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.578	1.573	1.567	1.572
Volumetric water content (%)	37.863	36.536	39.023	36.858
Hydraulic conductivity (cm/h)	973.926	1097.623	988.643	1055.361
Pore velocity (cm/h)	64.515	68.127	62.702	65.273
Bromide total mass recovery (%)	94 ± 1	97 ± 1	95 ± 1	93 ± 1
Glyphosate total mass recovery (%)	90 ± 1	92 ± 1	91 ± 1	92 ± 1
<i>Triton X-100 experiments</i>				
Soil Mass (g)	50.487	50.647	50.545	50.328
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.570	1.575	1.572	1.565
Volumetric water content (%)	37.568	36.784	38.479	35.248
Hydraulic conductivity (cm/h)	984.351	981.145	995.145	1045.214
Pore velocity (cm/h)	65.145	63.158	64.129	66.248
Bromide total mass recovery (%)	96 ± 1	95 ± 1	97 ± 1	93 ± 1
Triton X-100 total mass recovery (%)	93 ± 1	94 ± 1	96 ± 1	95 ± 1

densities of the used agricultural soils, the uniform packing method yielded soil columns with closely comparable characteristics, including hydraulic conductivity, porosity, and pore velocity. The small variations observed in hydraulic conductivities determined by falling head approach (Sandoval et al., 2017), are likely attributed to differences in soil physical properties and chemical composition heterogeneity. Also, the mass recovery of the compounds, further validates the reliability of the experiments.

Figs. 3 and 4 display the results obtained from the single component column experiments for glyphosate and Triton X-100, providing a visual representation of breakthrough curves (BTCs) in agricultural soils. Each case has been repeated three times independently, with a new soil column to ensure the repeatability and the validity of the data, as documented in Appendix B. The BTCs of bromide in all experiments exhibit remarkable uniformity across all four agricultural soils. These observations are complemented by dispersion parameters presented in Table 5 where according to the inverse model results, the dispersion coefficient across all soil columns is nearly identical (~0.270 cm²/h), ensuring consistent transport conditions in the experimental setup. Moreover, results show that there is negligible tailing in the tracer transport, suggesting that the movement of the tracer through the soil columns is not significantly affected by any retarding mechanisms. Furthermore, any observed tailing or retardation effects in the glyphosate and Triton X-100 BTCs are attributed to the specific sorption–desorption and transport characteristics of themselves.

The results from the single sorption experiments demonstrate significant tailing and a longer travel time (the duration it takes for the chemical to travel from the inlet to the outlet of the column) for glyphosate in the BTCs compared to that of bromide. It is important to note that, although glyphosate is typically considered a non-mobile compound, its leaching in this study is notably higher than what has been reported in previous research (Cederlund et al., 2017). This increased leaching is attributed to the continuous high flow rate used in the experiments, simulating a scenario for glyphosate movement through soil and into groundwater resources. As the agricultural soil columns were uniformly packed in this study, no preferential flow due to the presence of potential macropores is formed, and thus, the longer travel time for glyphosate is attributed to the sorption–desorption process. Triton X-100 exhibits significantly shorter tailing, and retardation compared to glyphosate. Due to the presence of a phosphonate group in glyphosate's structure, this pesticide exhibits a strong affinity for Fe/Al oxides and the edge sites of phyllosilicates, which are commonly found in agricultural soils. This characteristic significantly enhances the sorption capacity of glyphosate. While hydrophilic characteristic of Triton X-100 reduces Triton X-100 tendency to interact with soil particles (Li et al., 2020). This difference in chemical characteristics accounts for the lower sorption and reduced retardation of Triton X-100 compared to glyphosate. This behaviour is attributed to its non-ionic nature, as the sorption of Triton X-100 is primarily controlled by hydrophobic interactions with soil organic matter rather than electrostatic forces. Given that the soils in this study exhibit similarly low organic carbon contents and surface characteristics, their sorption capacities toward Triton X-100 are expected to be comparable. Moreover, due to the high solubility and low affinity of Triton X-100 for mineral surfaces, the influence of soil texture and mineral composition remains limited.

Best-fit model parameters of sorption and desorption for describing glyphosate and Triton X-100 BTCs are given in Table 5. Equilibrium models indicate that, even under high flow rates, compared to Triton X-100 glyphosate presents a significantly lower leaching due to its high sorption coefficients, greater nonlinearity, and larger sorption capacities in our agricultural soils. The Freundlich model demonstrates that glyphosate's sorption behaviour is nonlinear across all soils, as indicated by a nonlinearity parameter (Average $m_{\text{Glyphosate}} \sim 0.84$). Furthermore, the Langmuir model highlights a high maximum sorption capacity for glyphosate (up to 20 mg/g_{soil}). In contrast, Triton X-100 exhibits minimal sorption, characterized by low sorption coefficients, a nearly linear

Fig. 3. Leaching results for bromide and glyphosate in single sorption a) soil a; b) soil b; c) soil c; d) soil d. the black dashed line is the start of the test after 60 min pre-equilibrium.

Fig. 4. Leaching results for bromide and triton x-100 in single sorption a) soil a; b) soil b; c) soil c; d) soil d. the black dashed line test start after 60 min pre-equilibrium.

behaviour with a nonlinearity parameter close to one, and a much lower maximum sorption capacity according to the Langmuir model. Another key factor illustrating the impact of sorption mechanisms on the leaching and transport of these compounds is the retardation factor. In the linear model, retardation is solely dependent on the sorption coefficient and remains constant, regardless of concentration.

However, in the Freundlich and Langmuir models, the retardation factor varies with concentration and here this parameter changes over time based on the concentration values at the bottom of the column. The maximum retardation factors (R_{max}) are presented to enable a consistent comparison of the delay and retardation occurring within the soil

column due to sorption mechanisms across different soil types. The MLM calculation for R_{max} across different models demonstrates that glyphosate exhibits significantly higher retardation factors in all cases, in stark contrast to Triton X-100, which shows minimal sorption and low retardation (see Fig. 4). Based on the MLM and Langmuir models, which provide the highest accuracy among the equilibrium models, the R_{max} values for glyphosate varies between 15 and over 30, depending on soil characteristics. In comparison, R_{max} for Triton X-100 is consistently less than 10, indicating minimal delay in all agricultural soils.

Equilibrium models are limited in determining desorption and the ratio between sorption and desorption coefficients, leading to low

Table 5

MLM based estimates of the values for transport and sorption models resting on the data from independent single Glyphosate and Triton X-100 transport experiments.

Parameters	Glyphosate				Triton X-100			
	Soil A	Soil B	Soil C	Soil D	Soil A	Soil B	Soil C	Soil D
D (cm ² /h)	0.275	0.273	0.270	0.271	0.268	0.278	0.271	0.281
Linear models								
Equilibrium linear								
K_d (L/g _{soil})	2.275	1.334	1.976	1.189	0.163	0.127	0.139	0.118
R_{Linear} (-)	10.464	4.895	8.934	2.764	1.679	1.546	1.558	1.503
$R_{Equilibrium}^2$ (-)	0.715	0.733	0.728	0.722	0.734	0.739	0.715	0.748
RMSE _{Equilibrium}	4.985	3.658	3.127	4.186	0.154	0.165	0.189	0.147
Kinetic linear								
$k_{sor,d}$ (L/g _{soil} ·h)	2.738	1.763	2.234	1.998	0.249	0.1852	0.218	0.175
$k_{des,d}$ (1/h)	1.342	1.025	1.381	1.143	0.218	0.176	0.207	0.163
$R_{Kinetic}^2$ (-)	0.739	0.753	0.712	0.734	0.715	0.751	0.735	0.729
RMSE _{Kinetic}	5.372	4.182	4.423	4.283	0.148	0.157	0.182	0.152
Freundlich models								
Equilibrium Freundlich								
K_F (L ^m /mg ^{1-m} ·g _{soil})	1.735	1.134	1.458	1.072	0.182	0.167	0.172	0.163
m (-)	0.636	0.788	0.789	0.968	0.941	0.965	0.997	0.969
R_{max} , Freundlich (-)	22.397	9.780	15.067	4.452	2.811	2.626	2.272	2.251
$R_{Equilibrium}^2$ (-)	0.723	0.716	0.736	0.732	0.738	0.723	0.732	0.737
RMSE _{Equilibrium}	4.693	3.834	3.056	3.943	0.143	0.163	0.176	0.144
Kinetic Freundlich								
$k_{sor,F}$ (L ^m ·mg ^{1-m} /h·g _{soil})	1.924	1.492	1.732	1.243	0.192	0.171	0.182	0.174
m (-)	0.753	0.914	0.846	0.825	0.988	0.977	0.932	0.973
$k_{des,F}$ (1/h)	1.142	1.253	1.582	1.198	0.178	0.156	0.162	0.169
$R_{Kinetic}^2$ (-)	0.792	0.793	0.803	0.804	0.792	0.785	0.798	0.804
RMSE _{Kinetic}	3.746	3.473	3.238	3.392	0.148	0.161	0.169	0.152
Langmuir models								
Equilibrium Langmuir								
K_L (L/mg)	36.262	24.251	29.612	22.447	4.643	2.618	3.622	2.602
S_{max} (mg/g _{soil})	21.154	9.214	11.215	9.658	0.155	0.143	0.132	0.126
R_{max} , Langmuir (-)	33.261	17.261	22.921	15.142	9.944	8.646	9.545	7.541
$R_{Equilibrium}^2$ (-)	0.832	0.841	0.822	0.831	0.825	0.817	0.826	0.833
RMSE _{Equilibrium}	3.183	2.938	2.837	2.374	0.128	0.131	0.139	0.122
Kinetic Langmuir								
$k_{sor,L}$ (L/mg·h)	41.262	28.351	35.271	24.172	4.162	3.271	3.461	3.192
S_{max} (mg/g _{soil})	20.214	8.957	10.596	9.123	0.197	0.186	0.117	0.175
$k_{des,L}$ (1/h)	33.161	23.192	31.271	21.182	1.712	1.271	1.521	1.129
$R_{Kinetic}^2$ (-)	0.893	0.879	0.898	0.882	0.883	0.893	0.903	0.889
RMSE _{Kinetic}	2.837	2.536	2.362	2.193	0.121	0.126	0.126	0.118

accurate predictions of BTCs. As a result, kinetic models become indispensable, particularly under elevated flow rate conditions such as during heavy rainfall or intensive irrigation where flow rates can reach up to 95.473 (cm/h), and equilibrium models may fail to accurately capture the sorption behaviour. Providing a comparison between coefficients of sorption rates across all kinetic models for agricultural soils, results shows that glyphosate exhibits significantly higher sorption rate compared to Triton X-100, which has minimal sorption during dynamic processes. Moreover, The kinetic models based on Freundlich non-linearity term (m) reveal much greater nonlinearity in glyphosate sorption-desorption and a substantially higher maximum sorption capacity based on kinetic Langmuir model (S_{max}). Based on the models' performance in this study, as indicated by R^2 and RMSE values, kinetic models demonstrate, on average, a 10% higher accuracy compared to equilibrium models. Notably, the kinetic Langmuir model emerges as

the most accurate for capturing the sorption dynamics of the compounds studied ($R^2 > 0.87$ and $RMSE < 2.6$ mg/L). The reliability of the kinetic Langmuir model lies in its ability to accurately incorporate kinetic sorption-desorption rate coefficients and the sorption capacity specific to each chemical and soil type. This model assumes a finite number of sorption sites for the compounds, effectively capturing the saturation of these sites. This is a factor when addressing high concentrations, where other models, fail to provide an adequate description.

To interpret sorption-desorption behaviour across different agricultural soils, it is essential to account for several factors, including pH, particle size, and soil composition. Fig. 5 presents the normalised BTCs for glyphosate and Triton X-100 in single component experiments across various agricultural soils. The results indicate that Triton X-100 exhibits consistent leaching behaviour in all soils, as reflected by nearly identical BTCs and similar sorption and desorption coefficients across different

Fig. 5. Comparison of normalised outlet concentration (leaching) results for a) glyphosate and b) Triton X-100 in four soil columns in single sorption analysis. The black dashed line shows the start of the test after 60 min pre-equilibrium phase.

models as presented in Table 5.

The results indicate that the sorption of Triton X-100 across different agricultural soils is small with a low retardation due to its low sorption affinity. In contrast, the sorption, desorption, and retardation of glyphosate which has a high sorption affinity, vary significantly between soils. This behaviour are mainly attributed to differences in soil composition, including both organic and inorganic components. Based on the results of LOI and XRF/XRD analyses, the agricultural soils display similar organic content but differ significantly in mineralogical composition. Based on kinetic Langmuir model, soil A shows the highest sorption capacity for glyphosate (20.214 mg/g_{soil}), resulting in a significantly longer travel time approximately 200 min after injection. In contrast, Soils B and D exhibit much shorter travel times for glyphosate, with delays of only about 30 min, as well as similar sorption and desorption rates, according to kinetic models. glyphosate demonstrates a notable affinity for binding to minerals present in agricultural soils, and its sorption capacity is strongly influenced by the mineral composition. Soils A and C, which contain higher amounts of Albite, Illite, and Kaolinite compared to soils B and D, exhibit improved glyphosate sorption capacity. These minerals, known for their surface area, provide numerous binding sites for glyphosate, enhancing its retention in these soils (Guo et al., 2021). Recent studies have highlighted that minerals such as Albite (de Menezes and da Silva, 2016), Illite (Jabin et al., 2021), and Kaolinite (Al-Essa and Khalili, 2018) enhance the sorption capacity of agricultural soils for various chemicals, including pesticides. Moreover, the presence of specific metal oxides and cations, such as iron, potassium, and aluminium, further amplifies glyphosate's sorption, as established in the literature (Junqueira et al., 2020; Ololade et al., 2014). Soil A, which exhibits the highest glyphosate sorption among the studied soils, can be directly linked to its elevated amounts of aluminium (6.249%), potassium (8.384%), and iron (29.74%) which enhance the soil's ability to retain glyphosate, leading to prolonged travel times and higher retardation (Gairhe et al., 2021). The sorption and removal efficiency of glyphosate in the agricultural soils investigated in this study is considerably lower compared to commonly used sorbents, as summarized in Appendix E. These alternative sorbents, including biochar,

activated carbon, and Zeolite, have demonstrated glyphosate removal efficiencies of up to 90% in various environmental applications.

3.2. Competitive sorption

Based on the results of the single compound analysis, the same experimental approach but competitive models are applied to investigate the sorption–desorption dynamics between glyphosate and Triton X-100 across agricultural soils. The key attributes of the soil columns used in the competitive experiments are detailed in Table 6. Similar to the single sorption analysis, the same packing method was employed to ensure consistent characteristics, including hydraulic conductivity, porosity, and pore velocity across the soil columns, allowing for accurate assessment of competitive sorption effects on glyphosate transport. Additionally, similar to the single sorption experiments, the mass recovery of the compounds is performed to confirm the accuracy and reliability of the experimental setup. The mass recovery for both glyphosate and Triton X-100 ranges from 90 to 96%. This indicates that losses due to degradation or irreversible sorption were minimal under the experimental conditions. Consequently, the sorption behaviour observed in this study is predominantly reversible, justifying the use of the extended and kinetic competitive Langmuir models. The high recovery further supports that the sorption–desorption dynamics, rather than chemical transformation or permanent retention, control the transport and fate of these compounds in the soil system.

Fig. 6 presents BTCs for bromide, glyphosate, and Triton X-100 in a 12-hour experiment, encompassing the initial pre-equilibrium phase, chemicals injection, and DDW injection periods. Based on the BTCs, similar to the single sorption–desorption experiments, the transport behaviour of bromide is nearly identical across different soil columns. This is further supported by the dispersion coefficients estimated using MLM, which show an average value of 0.266 cm²/h with only minor deviations across the various cases. These results indicate uniform transport behaviour of bromide across different agricultural soils, reflecting consistent dispersion characteristics despite the variations in soil properties. The BTC results are further supported by inversely estimated values of the competitive sorption and desorption models resting on the measured glyphosate and Triton X-100 concentrations, as presented in Table 7.

The BTCs for Triton X-100 in the competitive scenario, compared to single conditions, reveal minimal changes in its transport and sorption–desorption behaviour in the presence of glyphosate for all agricultural soils. The travel time remains consistent, while both retardation and tailing effects are minimal. This is attributed to Triton X-100's inherently low sorption capacity, even at high aqueous-phase concentrations, rendering the presence of glyphosate which competes for sorption sites, does not significantly alter its sorption–desorption dynamics. This observation is further supported by the kinetic and equilibrium competitive sorption–desorption models derived from MLM,

Table 6
Characteristics of soil columns for competitive sorption experiments.

Parameter	Soil A	Soil B	Soil C	Soil D
Soil Mass (g)	50.313	50.429	50.183	50.642
Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.565	1.569	1.561	1.575
Volumetric water content (%)	38.364	36.736	39.233	36.711
Hydraulic conductivity (cm/h)	902.349	1045.541	1010.041	1118.895
Pore velocity (cm/h)	63.649	66.965	62.823	68.341
Bromide mass recovery (%)	95 ± 1	93 ± 1	96 ± 1	94 ± 1
Glyphosate total mass recovery (%)	91 ± 1	93 ± 1	92 ± 1	93 ± 1
Triton X-100 total mass recovery (%)	94 ± 1	95 ± 1	93 ± 1	96 ± 1

Fig. 6. Results of column test experiments for competitive sorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in agricultural soils: a) Soil A; b) Soil B; c) Soil C; d) Soil D. The black dashed line shows the start of the test after 60 min pre-equilibrium phase.

Table 7

Dispersion and competitive sorption–desorption models parameters for glyphosate and Triton X-100 estimated by MLM according to the equilibrium and kinetic models.

Soil	D (cm ² /h)	Extended Langmuir Equilibrium Model		
		K _{L, Gly} (L/mg)	K _{L, Tr} (L/mg)	S _{max} (mg/g _{soil})
Soil A	0.268	20.819	3.957	18.497
Soil B	0.272	17.215	2.445	7.836
Soil C	0.264	19.364	3.162	10.953
Soil D	0.262	18.458	2.392	8.219

Kinetic Competitive Langmuir Model							
	k _{sor, Gly} (L/mg-h)	k _{des, Gly} (1/h)	ε _{Gly} (-)	k _{sor, Triton} (L/mg-h)	k _{des, Triton} (1/h)	ε _{Triton} (-)	S _{max} (mg/g _{soil})
Soil A	23.612	15.821	0.252	3.726	1.772	0.748	18.245
Soil B	13.271	9.261	0.263	2.862	1.328	0.737	8.259
Soil C	19.267	11.272	0.192	3.182	1.610	0.808	9.489
Soil D	11.261	9.261	0.162	2.773	1.172	0.838	8.157

Model Performance				
	Extended Langmuir		Kinetic Langmuir	
	R ²	RMSE	R ²	RMSE
Soil A	0.813	4.152	0.893	4.182
Soil B	0.846	4.292	0.887	4.521
Soil C	0.824	4.362	0.916	4.421
Soil D	0.832	4.161	0.893	4.392

which show minimal changes in sorption–desorption coefficients and nonlinearity parameters. In contrast, the competitive scenario markedly affects glyphosate’s transport and sorption–desorption behaviour. Based on BTCs, the travel time, retardation, and tailing of glyphosate decrease in all agricultural soils when Triton X-100 is present, where this effect is more pronounced in soils with higher sorption capacities. In soil A, which had the highest sorption and retardation in the single sorption–desorption experiments, glyphosate’s travel time dropped dramatically from 200 min in the single-solute case to just 50 min in the competitive scenario, indicating a significant difference. In soil C, the

travel time was reduced by about 50%, while in soils B and D, which initially exhibited the lowest travel times, the differences were minor.

Results from the MLM quantitatively demonstrate significant changes in the sorption–desorption behaviour of glyphosate in the presence of Triton X-100, reinforcing the findings from the BTCs analysis. The equilibrium model Extended Langmuir offer a comparative analysis of transport delays caused by sorption mechanisms within soil columns. Results indicate that, the sorption of glyphosate decreases under competitive conditions compared to single-compound scenarios for all soils. This reduction is most pronounced in soils A and C, which

previously showed high sorption capacities and retardation in single-sorption experiments, are more significantly affected because their higher availability of sorption sites makes them more susceptible to competitive displacement. The presence of Triton X-100 likely reduces glyphosate's access to these sites by either physically occupying the sites or altering the chemical environment, such as by changing surface charges or blocking access to high-affinity binding sites. For soils B and D, which have lower sorption capacities, the competition exerts a smaller effect because the already limited sorption sites provide less opportunity for competitive exclusion, resulting in minimal changes to sorption behaviour.

The results from the kinetic competitive Langmuir model indicate minimal changes in the sorption and desorption rates, as well as their associated ratios, for Triton X-100 compared to single-sorption conditions. This confirms that competition with glyphosate has a negligible impact on Triton X-100's leaching and sorption over time in soil systems. In contrast, for glyphosate, the variations in sorption and desorption rate coefficients under competitive conditions reveal a significant narrowing of the sorption-to-desorption ratio ($K_{\text{sor}}/K_{\text{desor}}$) across soils A, B, C, and D, with reductions of 23%, 13%, 19%, and 6%, respectively. These impacts are more pronounced in soils A and C, which exhibit higher sorption capacities. This suggests that although competitive interactions reduce both the sorption and desorption coefficients, they ultimately bring glyphosate's sorption and desorption rates closer together, indicating a reduction in sorption capacity over time for this pesticide. In the competitive scenario, the presence of Triton X-100 and the resulting competition between compounds weakens glyphosate's ability to bind strongly to the soil matrix. Consequently, glyphosate is less likely to be retained in the soil, facilitating faster transport through the soil profile. Compared to competitive equilibrium Extended Langmuir, the competitive kinetic model achieves an average improvement of approximately 5% in goodness-of-fit metrics and around 10% in RMSE coefficients. This highlights the superior accuracy of the kinetic model in representing the system. Furthermore, the model captures the variations in sorption and desorption rate coefficients, effectively accounting for the temporal dynamics of compound interactions. This capability is particularly crucial under high-flow-rate conditions, where equilibrium models lack the accuracy.

Another important insight from the kinetic Langmuir model as the most accurate model in competitive condition is the maximum sorption capacity of agricultural soils. In the single sorption scenario, the Langmuir model estimates the maximum sorption capacity for one compound, while in the competitive case, this capacity reflects the combined sorption potential for both compounds simultaneously. The results indicate a slight decrease in the total maximum sorption capacity under competitive conditions compared to the sum of individual capacities from single sorption experiments for glyphosate and Triton X-100. This reduction is observed across all agricultural soils, with soil A showing a 7% decrease, soil B 5%, soil C 10%, and soil D 6%. The reduced overall sorption potential suggests that competitive sorption limits the availability of binding sites for both glyphosate and Triton X-100. When these compounds compete for sorption on soil particles, the finite number of binding sites becomes crucial. This competition lowers sorption efficiency, as sites are either occupied by one compound or obstructed by the other, reducing overall sorption capacity (Azimzadeh et al., 2024; Rezazadeh et al., 2023). This effect, particularly evident in soils with high sorption capacity (soils A and C), emphasizes the complexity of multi-compound interactions in agricultural environments. The competitive sorption-desorption pathways of Glyphosate and Triton X-100 within high flow rate conditions are a function of presented analysis which determine the fate and contamination potential of these

compounds as presented in Appendix F. Some of the key potential mechanisms that may influence the observed competitive sorption, though not directly quantified in this study, include electrostatic interactions between glyphosate and positively charged sites or metal oxides, due to glyphosate's high polarity (Azimzadeh et al., 2024; Geyssels et al., 2026). While this analysis relies on modelling and column experiments to infer these mechanisms, future studies could incorporate spectroscopic or microscopic techniques to directly observe surface interactions and provide further mechanistic validation. Additionally, Triton X-100 may sorb onto soil particles via hydrophobic interactions, forming surface layers that block access to sorption sites. This can introduce steric hindrance, thereby preventing glyphosate molecules from effectively reaching and binding to available sites.

3.3. Effects of environmental factors, challenges in generalization

The results of single and competitive sorption-desorption analyses for glyphosate and Triton X-100 under high flow rate conditions, representing a high leaching scenario, reveal that for the surfactant Triton X-100, the sorption-desorption behaviour appears to be relatively consistent, as variations in soil composition and competition conditions tend to have a limited, though not negligible, influence on its behaviour. In contrast, for the pesticide glyphosate, it is not possible to generalize leaching and sorption-desorption dynamics. Changes in soil composition and the presence of the surfactant substantially influence glyphosate's leaching and sorption-desorption behaviour to varying extents, making its behaviour highly context-dependent and unsuitable for generalization. Here, the term generalization refers to the ability to observe consistent leaching and sorption-desorption behaviour for a specific compound under varying conditions. To further explore this, the effects of the concentration ratio between the pesticide and surfactant, as well as flow rate variations, are examined and presented in this section. To evaluate the influence of the concentration ratio between Triton X-100 and glyphosate on their competitive sorption-desorption, an independent experiment was performed using soil A, applying a 2% concentration of Triton X-100 where all other conditions are kept the same. Subsequently, the effects of 0%, 1%, and 2% Triton X-100 concentrations in single and competitive scenarios with a fixed glyphosate concentration of 100 mg/L were compared. Fig. 7a and b illustrate the competitive sorption-desorption behaviour in soil A for Triton X-100 at concentrations of 1% and 2%. The first observation is the consistent behaviour of the tracer across different concentration ratios, as indicated by the nearly constant dispersion coefficient ($D_{0\% \text{ Triton}} = 0.275 \text{ cm}^2/\text{h}$, $D_{1\% \text{ Triton}} = 0.268 \text{ cm}^2/\text{h}$, $D_{2\% \text{ Triton}} = 0.271 \text{ cm}^2/\text{h}$), confirming no significant effect on tracer transport within the soil columns. Fig. 7c illustrates the BTCs for glyphosate across three concentrations of Triton X-100 (0%, 1%, and 2%), emphasizing the variations in its sorption and transport.

Results demonstrate that the presence of Triton X-100, coupled with an increase in its concentration from 1% to 2%, has a substantial impact on the leaching and sorption-desorption behaviour of glyphosate in agricultural soil. A comparison of BTCs in Fig. 7c for glyphosate at Triton X-100 concentrations of 1% and 2% reveals that doubling the surfactant concentration results in a slight decrease in retardation, unchanged tailing, and a notable reduction in the soil's sorption capacity. These observations can be further elucidated by integrating them with MLM results derived from the kinetic Langmuir model. MLM results show sorption coefficient $K_{\text{sor, Gly}}$ (L/mg-h) decreases about 10% (from 23.612 to 21.021) and the maximum sorption capacity of soil A for glyphosate is decreased from 18.245 mg/g_{soil} to 15.234 mg/g_{soil}. Doubling the concentration of Triton X-100 in the aqueous phase intensifies competition

Fig. 7. Effects of surfactant concentration on competitive sorption–desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100 for soil A. a) Triton X-100 concentration of 1%, b) Triton X-100 concentration of 2%, c) comparison of glyphosate concentration profiles with different Triton X-100 concentrations.

for available sorption sites, thereby reducing the binding opportunities for glyphosate. Although Triton X-100 exhibits a much lower sorption capacity compared to glyphosate, its higher concentration exacerbates the competition between the compounds. This significantly impairs glyphosate's ability to adsorb onto soil particles, resulting in reduced sorption capacity and a faster breakthrough of glyphosate during transport. Furthermore, the results indicate that doubling the Triton X-100 concentration causes no significant change in the tailing of glyphosate's BTC. This observation suggests that glyphosate's desorption

behaviour remains relatively unaffected, as corroborated by MLM results, which show that the desorption coefficient remains nearly constant (15.821 1/h to 15.839 1/h). This indicates that Triton X-100 primarily impacts the initial sorption dynamics without substantially altering glyphosate's retention and release mechanisms. The consistent tailing may imply that glyphosate's desorption is governed by other factors, such as its stronger binding to high-affinity sites or specific interactions with soil components that are less influenced by the presence of Triton X-100.

Fig. 8. Effects of flow rate on competitive sorption–desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100. a) Flow rate 2 ml/min; b) Flow rate 3 ml/min; c) comparison of glyphosate concentration profiles with different flow rates.

An additional independent experiment was conducted with all conditions held constant while the flow rate was increased from 2 ml/min to 3 ml/min. This investigation aimed to further explore the influence of flow rate on the transport and competitive sorption–desorption dynamics of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in agricultural soil to enhance the understanding of how high flow rate conditions such as those encountered during heavy rainfall and intensive irrigation impact the leaching and interactions of these substances within the soil matrix. The experiments were conducted with a focus on soil A, characterized by its notably high sorption capacity. Fig. 8a–b display the BTCs for bromide, glyphosate, and Triton X-100 at flow rates of 2 ml/min and 3 ml/min. Meanwhile, Fig. 8c provides a comparison of the BTCs for glyphosate, highlighting the differences between single and competitive sorption scenarios with different flow rates. In both flow rates, the BTCs of bromide show minimal retardation and tailing, confirming that its movement is primarily advective and there is no retarding mechanism influencing the transport of this compound. However, in the case of the higher flow rate (3 ml/min), bromide reaches the peak concentration slightly faster due to the shorter residence time within the soil column. Moreover, with the increased flow rate at 3 ml/min, dispersion also increases. This is evident from the broader BTCs, indicating that a higher flow rate creates more heterogeneity in flow paths within the soil column. The higher dispersion at 3 ml/min results in less uniform transport, where some portions of the solute are transported rapidly, while others are retained longer, contributing to the spread in BTC peaks. This is confirmed by the estimated dispersion values that demonstrate solute dispersion increases from 0.268 cm²/h at a flow rate of 2 ml/min to 0.314 cm²/h at 3 ml/min. The elevated flow rate enhances the transport of chemicals and amplifies the potential for uneven flow paths and variations in flow velocities within the soil, resulting in a broader distribution of solute particles and increased dispersion over time. The BTCs for Triton X-100 at a flow rate of 2 ml/min show a smoother curve compared to the higher flow rate of 3 ml/min, indicating more time for the chemicals to interact with the soil matrix, leading to increased sorption and slower transport. This observation is further supported by MLM results, where the estimated sorption coefficient based on the kinetic Langmuir model shows a slight decrease from 3.726 to 3.469 (L/mg·h), while the desorption coefficient increases slightly from 1.772 to 1.819 (1/h). Despite these differences, both the BTCs and the MLM results suggest that due to Triton X-100's inherently low sorption capacity, increasing the flow rate does not have a particularly significant impact on reducing its sorption.

For glyphosate, which exhibits a higher sorption affinity, the effects of flow rate on its leaching and sorption–desorption behaviour are more pronounced. Comparing BTCs for glyphosate at two different flow rates presents challenges due to differences in pore volumes and injected mass. However, analysing the time-variation BTCs in Fig. 8a–b reveals that at a flow rate of 2 ml/min, glyphosate's BTC is more elongated, signifying enhanced sorption and prolonged retention within the soil matrix. Conversely, at a higher flow rate of 3 ml/min, glyphosate breaks through earlier, displaying a sharper peak and faster elution, attributed to an increase in desorption. This behaviour arises from reduced interaction time between glyphosate and the soil matrix, limiting the sorption capacity and resulting in decreased retardation. Supporting this, MLM results indicate that increasing the flow rate from 2 to 3 ml/min reduces the sorption coefficient from 23.612 to 18.734 (L/mg·h) and slightly increases the desorption coefficient from 15.821 to 16.283 (1/h). Based on Fig. 8c, increasing the flow rate leads to a higher mass of glyphosate being injected into the soil column, highlighting the importance of comparing the injected mass with the sorbed amount to assess the effects on sorption capacity. At a flow rate of 2 ml/min, 0.048 g of

glyphosate was injected, while 0.072 g was introduced at 3 ml/min. Analysis of the BTCs in Fig. 8c shows that the actual sorbed mass is 0.0172 g for 2 ml/min and 0.0115 g for 3 ml/min. This corresponds to approximately 36% sorption at 2 ml/min compared to only about 16% at 3 ml/min. These results indicate that increasing the flow rate reduces the overall sorption capacity of glyphosate, likely due to the shorter interaction time between glyphosate and the soil matrix, which limits the sorption process at higher flow rates. Increased desorption of glyphosate under high-flow agricultural conditions may enhance its transport to groundwater, raising concerns about ecological toxicity. Even at low concentrations, glyphosate has been shown to adversely affect aquatic organisms. Its increased mobility under dynamic flow conditions can lead to more frequent and intense pulses in receiving waters, thereby contributing to the long-term contamination of freshwater ecosystems.

The results of leaching and competitive sorption–desorption for glyphosate and Triton X-100 under varying soil composition, concentration ratios, and flow rates representing common environmental factors demonstrate that leaching, sorption, and desorption behaviours within high-flow conditions, characteristic of a kinetic framework, can exhibit either reductive or enhancing trends for each mechanism. This highlights that sorption–desorption characteristics related to a particular tested soils, flow rates, and concentration ranges, may not be directly applicable to other soil types or environmental conditions. Consequently, sorption–desorption coefficients estimated from a specific case should not be directly applied to forward modelling of other cases without accounting for the effects of varying parameters and concentration ratios.

While this study was conducted under laboratory column conditions, the estimated sorption–desorption parameters provide useful insights for field applications. When scaling to field conditions, factors such as soil heterogeneity, preferential flow paths, microbial activity, and seasonal variations in moisture and temperature should be considered, as they can influence both the magnitude and kinetics of sorption–desorption processes. Laboratory-derived parameters may be adapted to field-scale models through upscaling approaches, including inverse modelling using field observations or averaging over representative soil volumes.

4. Conclusion

Overall, this study provides insights into the competitive sorption–desorption and transport behaviours of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in agricultural soils under high flow rates simulating intense leaching conditions. These findings help optimize their use while minimizing groundwater contamination risks. Based on the experimental data and MLM analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- I. Within the competitive framework, where Triton X-100's sorption–desorption and transport are largely unaffected by glyphosate, the presence of Triton X-100 significantly reduces glyphosate's sorption and retardation across all soil types, particularly in soils with high sorption capacity (A and C). Also, competitive interactions between glyphosate and Triton X-100 result in a slight decrease in overall soil sorption capacity (soil A 7%, soil B 5%, soil C 10%, and soil D 6%), underscoring the significance of limited binding site availability when competitive compounds coexist in soil.
- II. In both single and competitive scenarios, kinetic models demonstrate 10% higher accuracy compared to equilibrium models. Notably, the kinetic Langmuir model emerges as the most

precise in capturing the sorption–desorption dynamics of glyphosate and Triton X-100 ($R^2 > 0.85$). This superiority is particularly evident under high flow rates of up to 3 mL/min, where equilibrium models fail to account for the time-dependent sorption–desorption mechanisms.

- III. Glyphosate demonstrates significantly higher sorption, tailing, and retardation in agricultural soils compared to Triton X-100, which has minimal and uniform sorption across all soil types regardless of soil characteristics. Glyphosate's high sorption affinity is attributed to its strong interactions with minerals like Albite, Illite, and Kaolinite, which contribute to prolonged retention. This effect is particularly notable in soils A and C, where higher concentrations of aluminium, potassium, and iron enhance glyphosate retention, further increasing its retardation and extending its travel time.
- IV. Doubling the concentration of Triton X-100 in soil A reduces the glyphosate sorption coefficient by 10% and decreases the maximum sorption capacity from 18.245 mg/g soil to 15.234 mg/g soil, while the desorption coefficient remains nearly constant (15.821 1/h to 15. /h). This highlights the distinct and varying impacts of concentration ratios on the sorption and desorption behaviours of glyphosate within competitive framework.
- V. Increasing the flow rate by 50% under high-flow conditions has minimal impact on Triton X-100 sorption–desorption behaviour but significantly affects glyphosate. The sorption coefficient of glyphosate decreases from 23.612 to 18.734 (L/mg·h), while the desorption coefficient increases slightly from 15.821 to 16.283 (1/h). Additionally, the sorption capacity drops from approximately 36% at a flow rate of 2 ml/min to about 16% at 3 ml/min. This highlights an increased risk of glyphosate leaching and groundwater contamination under conditions of heavy rainfall or high irrigation rates in agricultural soils where glyphosate and Triton X-100 coexist.
- VI. Following literature that the sorption behaviour of a specific pesticide and surfactant cannot be generalized across different chemical types, the results here highlight an even narrower specificity. For each unique combination of pesticide and surfactant, variations in soil composition, concentration ratios, and flow rates cannot be generalized across different scenarios. Variation of these environmental factors can significantly impact leaching and competitive sorption–desorption within the kinetic framework. Therefore, sorption–desorption coefficients estimated from one specific case should not be directly applied to

forward modelling in other cases without carefully considering the effects of varying parameters.

Future research building on this study should prioritize the development of a large-scale numerical model and the translation of column experiments and related models' coefficients to field conditions under various conditions. Additionally, the presence of natural organic matter, divalent cations, and microbial activity further affects the transport and retention of chemicals. While laboratory experiments and sorption–desorption models offer essential mechanistic understanding, field-scale investigations are crucial to validate these findings and assess their applicability under real-world environmental conditions, where complex interactions and heterogeneities cannot be fully captured in controlled laboratory settings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hamid Moghimi: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Mohaddeseh Mousavi Nezhad:** Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Marijke Huysmans:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A

Based on the chemical structure of the studied chemicals, the combination of IC-MS presents the swiftest and most precise method for detecting and quantifying glyphosate and Triton X-100. Glyphosate concentration measurement poses challenges due to its high polarity, low volatility, and lack of chromophores. While some studies suggested using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Valle et al., 2019), this method requires complex and time-consuming derivatization because of glyphosate's chemical structure. Alternatively, IC-MS proves to be an efficient method for detecting glyphosate, relying on its ionic metabolites. A time-efficient detection method for capturing potassium bromide, glyphosate, and Triton X-100 has been developed, enabling the analysis of all three chemicals within 25 min, inclusive of equilibration and measurement steps. This approach relies on a solvent gradient variation in column to achieve effective separation and detection of the target compounds. The method developed for ICP-MS measurements demonstrates a limit of quantification below 1 µg/L, enabling the detection of concentrations at low levels. As shown in Fig. A1 (a–c), calibration curves for each chemical were established using standard solution samples at different concentrations. To ensure accuracy, each calibration sample underwent analysis in triplicate using the IC-MS method. As per the Ion IC-MS method, Triton X-100 is the earliest compound detected at 5.026 min, followed by bromide at 8.57 min, and glyphosate at 12.80 min (Fig. A1, d, and e).

Fig. A1. Chromatography Calibration curves for a) bromide, b) glyphosate, c) Triton X-100. Detection results for d) Initial chemicals, e) Sample eluate of soil columns.

Appendix B

Each sorption experiment for all soils is conducted in independent triplicate to ensure the validity of the data and to quantify the maximum error within the system. To conserve space, the results are presented for the replicate tests conducted on one of the studied soils. As depicted in Fig. B1, the concentration curves for both the tracer and glyphosate closely overlap, indicating a prominent level of accuracy. Furthermore, the results outlined in Table B1 confirm that the maximum error within the system falls within acceptable limits, thereby validating the experimental data generated.

Table B1
Maximum measurements variance and errors for single and competitive sorption measurements for glyphosate, evaluating accuracy of generated data in column experiments.

	Soil A	Soil B	Soil C	Soil D
<i>Single sorption</i>				
Max. Variance (mg/L)	13.527	12.766	15.735	12.343
Max. Error (%)	8.759	7.735	9.826	6.263
<i>Competitive sorption</i>				
Max. Variance (mg/L)	13.527	15.873	14.285	16.889
Max. Error (%)	6.637	9.982	8.193	10.032

Fig. B1. Experimental replicates to ensure the validity of the generated data in a single sorption experiment for soil B. a) bromide. b) glyphosate.

In the column experiments, a constant up-flow percolation was maintained during both the saturation and solute transport phases to ensure stable hydraulic conditions and experimental repeatability. Altering the flow direction after saturation can induce transient flow regimes, air entrapment, and structural disturbance within the packed soil column, which may affect solute transport and complicate interpretation of breakthrough curves. Although under fully saturated conditions, natural leaching systems are typically characterised by gravity-driven downward flow when no significant boundary-induced pressure gradients are present, the adopted experimental design only focuses on controlled conditions to isolate sorption-desorption and transport processes. The implications of this simplification for field-scale applicability are therefore acknowledged.

Appendix C

Utilizing smaller columns offers significant advantages, such as reducing experimental costs, time, and chemical-soil usage. However, several challenges need to be addressed, including boundary effects, mass transfer limitations, and scale dependency of transport characteristics, which can potentially result in a reliable quantification of the transport process. To determine the appropriate column size with minimum size effect on solute transport mechanisms, the study referred to experiments conducted by (Naka et al., 2016), which explored various column sizes and experimental durations. Based on this reference, a standard ratio of 3 between column length and inner diameter (length/diameter) was selected. Accordingly, three different column sizes were chosen: large (210 mm × 70 mm), medium (150 mm × 50 mm), and small (75 mm × 25 mm) columns.

Fig. C1. Concentration of bromide in sandy soil using three columns (length/diameter = 3) with flow rate of 2 ml/min, a) 75 mm × 25 mm; b) 150 mm × 50 mm; and c) 210 mm × 70 mm.

The outcome of these three experiments presented in Fig. C1, demonstrates that larger columns require longer injection times, higher amounts of tracer injection, and longer travelling times, defined as the time required for the solute to reach the column outlet. The injection time is defined to ensure that the peak concentration within the column reaches the injected concentration of 100 mg/L. As presented by concentration profiles in Fig. C1, the overall behaviour of the transport process remains consistent across all three columns, and the boundary effects are successfully eliminated. Boundary effects include wall effects and end effects, both of which can influence solute transport within the column. Wall effects occur when interactions between the solute and the column walls disrupt flow dynamics, potentially leading to uneven solute distribution. End effects arise at the inlet and outlet of the column, where changes in flow dynamics can result in non-uniform solute distribution or altered transport characteristics. Despite using columns of varying sizes, we observed consistent transport behaviour, suggesting that boundary effects were negligible. We did not conduct separate experiments specifically to induce boundary effects. Instead, our approach was designed to inherently minimize any potential boundary effects through careful experimental design and column selection. The results generally indicate that the use of a smaller column (75 mm × 25 mm) has negligible effects on the transport, with minimal evidence of added tailing or boundary effects.

Appendix D

Fig. D1. Analytical and numerical solution for ADE comparing results of developed FTCS model with analytical solution results (Mojtabi and Deville, 2015) for initial condition $C(x, t = 0) = -\sin(\pi x)$ and boundary conditions $C(-1,t) = C(1,t) = 0$. a) Dispersion = $1/10\pi$, b) Dispersion = $1/100\pi$.

Appendix E

Table E1

Glyphosate removal efficiencies (%) reported in the literature for various types of common sorption media.

Sorption medium	Removal (%)	Reference
Biochar	50–80	(Wang et al., 2023)
Goethite	75–90	(Doyle et al., 2023)
Activated Carbon	50–85	(Sen and Mondal, 2022)
Zeolite	60–90	(Haghjoo et al., 2023)

Appendix F

Fig. F1. Conceptual diagram illustrating the sorption-desorption pathways.

Data availability

All data are available in the manuscript.

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